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The Indian Association of Music Therapy is the association which represents researcher, bio-musicologist, scientist, music therapists, corporate members and related associations worldwide to promote the use of music not only in the cure of various diseases but also for the healthy life.

IAMT founded in 2010 with a mission of establish music as a drug and progressive development of the therapeutic use of music in the cure of disorders and in rehabilitation, special education, and community settings. IAMT sets the education and clinical training standards for music therapists.

The main object of IAMT is-

- to protect our national heritage of music therapy available in our mythological literature and tribal areas
- to promote the scientific research in music therapy in zoology, botany, microbiology, medicine and other area of life sciences.
- to set up the guidelines in area of Music therapy.
- to start certificate, diploma and advance diploma training
- to set up a chain of music therapy centres and music therapy spa
- to start annual awards for the music therapist
- to start publication of journal of international repute so the work carried in the area of bio-musicology will be recognised at international platform
- take the initiative in music therapy and opened a new era of bio-musical research which minimize the use of drug in form of chemicals.
- to establish bio-musicology as a source of employment-For college students with a special, aptitude for music, but no desire for the bright lights of a performance carrier, music therapy is a field that offers opportunities and rewards. So it may become a tool of self-employment for college students of science and music.
- to organize seminar, conferences, workshops time to time

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